

Concerted European action on Sustainable Applications of REfractories

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Deliverable D6.1 - Data Management Plan

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Deliverable D6.1 Data Management Plan

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1 Introduction

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is a formal document that outlines what data will be processed and/or generated, and how they will be handled both during and after completion of CESAREF. The goal of a data management plan is to consider the many aspects of data management, metadata generation, data preservation and analysis to ensure that data are well-managed in the present and prepared for preservation in the future.

The DMP presents the standards that the consortium will use, how the data will be preserved and what data will be made available and published. Research data that are deemed to be exploitable for commercial purpose will be kept confidential either at the consortium level or at a specific work package level. Sensitive data provided by consortium partners will be kept confidential and anonymized if required.

The Data Management Plan is an evolving, public document and will gain more precision and substance during the project. It will be revised, if needed, to keep the information up to date.

2 Data Summary

Energy intensive industries, such as steel, cement, glass and super alloy producers, are key emitters of CO₂, with the Steel industry alone being responsible for 25 % of Europe's industrial CO₂ emissions and 7 % of the global industrial GHG emissions. The European Union aims to be climate-neutral by 2050 and this objective is at the heart of the European Green Deal. European Steel producers have already committed themselves to be fully Net Zero by 2050 which will entail the development and use of alternative breakthrough technologies and processes. CESAREF will help reach these targets through a range of approaches focussed on sustainable actions related to refractory materials. Refractory ceramics are one of the common factors across these energy intensive industries as their mechanical and thermomechanical properties make them ideal candidates for used as linings in high temperature environments. The four key approaches of the CESAREF network are:

- the employment of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) techniques to focus on the efficient use of mineral resources and recycling,
- increase the sustainability of the refractories through the study of the microstructure design,
- carry out fundamental research anticipating the adoption of Hydrogen based technologies, and,
- development of digital twins to improve energy efficiency and durability.

The different parts of the project are based on existing techniques and concepts that will be used as general references. From there, a wide variety of data will be generated over the course of the project as many new models, techniques and methodologies will be developed.

Different types of data will be generated, from videos, spreadsheets, photos, codes, reports on data analysis, etc. Some data will be used by partners of the consortium for academic and/or industrial purposes. As an example, some videos from webinar records will be re-used for training purpose through the ELEANOR (Electronic Learning Network on Refractories) platform.

Data will be labelled as open or non-open based on the sharing policies in the Work Package (WP) generating it.

While WPs are defined to target one scientific approach specifically, data will be transferred from one to any other WP as required throughout the duration of the project. Data will follow rules and recommendations in terms of standards.

At this point in time, the size of the data to be generated or re-used cannot be estimated in detail.

Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 present a summary of the data produced per WP.

Table 1 - Work package 1 - Efficient use of mineral resources and recycling

Types and formats of data	
Life cycle inventory along the life cycle of refractory materials (including materials input and output, energy consumption, and emission associated).	xlsx, text, ecospold
Environmental impacts along the life cycle of refractory materials	xlsx, text, pdf
purpose of the data generation and its relation to the objectives	
Conducting life cycle assessment	Evaluating the environmental performance of refractory products
the expected size of the data	
Life cycle inventory and impacts	300 MB
origin/provenance of the data	
Life cycle inventory data	Ecoinvent database, Sphera Managed LCA Content, Primary data from Saint-Gobain, Tata Steel and RHI Magnesita, literature, stoichiometric calculation
Environmental impacts along the life cycle of refractory materials	Based on the life cycle inventory combined to characterization factors found in impact assessment methodologies (eg EF3.1 provided by JRC)
whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project	
Life cycle inventories	Refractory producers, steelmakers, policy makers, researchers in the field of LCA
Life cycle assessment results	Refractory producers, steelmakers, policy makers, researchers in the field of LCA

Table 2 - Work package 2 - Microstructure design for increased sustainability

Types and formats of data	
Literature review	.txt; .pdf; .docx
Experimental and computer analysis	.txt; .csv; .raw; .tiff; .vgl; .jpeg; .png; .xlsx; .dat; .py; .cpp; .inp; .lgddl; .odb; .xlsx; .dat; .brml; .eva; .uxd
Methodology development	.txt; .docx
Reports	.txt; .docx
purpose of the data generation and its relation to the objectives	
Literature review	To understand the subject and review current industry development
Experimental and computer analysis	To validate new material recipes; evaluate material properties and microstructure; analyse 3D microstructures; simulate and validate system variations; pre and post-processing purpose for simulation
Methodology development	Analysis of results; publication process and validation
Reports	Reporting and publication purpose
the expected size of the data	
Literature review	100's MB
Experimental and computer analysis	100's GB
Methodology development	10's GB
Reports	100's MB
origin/provenance of the data	
Literature review	Internal source
Experimental and computer analysis	Internal source
Methodology development	Internal source
Reports	Internal source
whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project	
Literature review	Researchers; raw material producers; refractory producers; end-users (e.g. steelmakers)
Experimental and computer analysis	Researchers; raw material producers; refractory producers; end-users (e.g. steelmakers)
Methodology development	Researchers; raw material producers; refractory producers; end-users (e.g. steelmakers)
Reports	Researchers; raw material producers; refractory producers; end-users (e.g. steelmakers)

Table 3 - Work package 3 - Anticipation of Hydrogen Steel Making

Types and formats of data	
Reporting	.docx/.doc
Thermomechanical tests; Factsage simulations	.xls
Microstructural analysis	.tif
Phase analysis	.uxd/.raw/.brml/.eva
purpose of the data generation and its relation to the objectives	
Reporting	Literature and reports
Thermomechanical tests; Factsage simulations	Temperature related refractory properties
Microstructural analysis	In-situ analysis of microstructural evolution
Phase analysis	Phase characterization of samples
the expected size of the data	
Reporting	100's MB
Thermomechanical tests / Facstage simulations	100's MB
Microstructural analysis	10's GB
Phase analysis	100's MB
origin/provenance of the data	
Reporting	Internal
Thermomechanical tests / Facstage simulations	Internal
Microstructural analysis	Internal
Phase analysis	Internal
whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project	
Reporting	Researchers, Raw material suppliers, steelmakers
Thermomechanical tests / Facstage simulations	Researchers, Raw material suppliers, steelmakers
Microstructural analysis	Researchers, Raw material suppliers, steelmakers
Phase analysis	Researchers, Raw material suppliers, steelmakers

Table 4 - Work package 4 - Energy efficiency and durability

Types and formats of data	
Source codes	Text files
Experimental/Computational results	Excel files; SQLite database files; .ipynb
Historical data of refractory temperature measurements	CSV files
Process information	CSV files
purpose of the data generation and its relation to the objectives	
Source codes	Thermal state definition, Prediction model, reduced order model, implementation of models, optimization routines, user interface, and data processing
Experimental/Computational results	Temperature prediction, thermal state estimation, reporting, and publication process, analysis of data and results
Historical data of refractory temperature measurements	Temperature prediction
Process information	History of the Ladle, online prediction, preheating/ tapping requirements, model validation
the expected size of the data	
Source codes	10's GB
Experimental results	100's GB
Historical data of refractory temperature measurements	10's GB
Process information	10's GB
origin/provenance of the data	
Source codes	Internal model
Experimental results	Internal model
Historical data of refractory temperature measurements	Database from industrial beneficiary
Process information	Database from industrial beneficiary
whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project	
Source codes	Researchers, steel making plants, software developers
Experimental results	Researchers, steel making plants
Historical data of refractory temperature measurements	Researchers
Process information	Researchers

3 FAIR data

This document considers the latest guidelines on FAIR data management in Horizon Europe. The CESAREF project partners should make their research data **findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR)** and ensure that it is managed correctly. Good research data management will lead to further knowledge discovery and innovation as well as the integration and reuse of subsequent data and knowledge.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

To keep data findable, it is necessary to provide its metadata. Metadata is a systematic method used to describe resources, improving access to them. Author, date created, date modified and file size are examples of very basic document metadata.

Considering the strong interdisciplinary nature of the CESAREF project, a broad and domain agnostic metadata standard that the EU recommends to its member states for recording information about research activity has been adopted. The Common European Research Information Format (CERIF) standard is described at <https://eurocris.org/services/main-features-cerif>.

The repository Zenodo will be used for data publishing. Persistent identifiers, such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOI), will be used for publication data, as it is one of the most common ways for data identification. The DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record. Zenodo's metadata is compliant with [DataCite's Metadata Schema](#) minimum and recommended terms. The metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing. The metadata of each record is also sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

The metadata are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol. Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the [OAI-PMH](#) protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public [REST API](#).

Currently, all data is stored either locally or in a dedicated, private, OneDrive file with the data subject, authors and change log history clearly indicated when necessary.

3.2 Making data accessible

The repository Zenodo, which provides persistent identifiers for data sets, will be used for the publication of data and metadata.

Due to the multi-beneficiary nature of the CESAREF project, some of whom are in direct competition, data sets providing commercially sensitive information will not be made public. Where possible, generic or anonymized data sets will be used, and made publicly available, thus avoiding the distribution of sensitive, product specific, information.

The open, free and universal protocols, for information retrieval on the web, [OAI-PMH](#) and [REST API](#) are used by Zenodo to ensure the data is accessible. Due to the nature of the data generated during this project, any data that is made accessible will be made publicly available and will not need approval through a dedicated committee, to gain access.

The metadata will be made openly available, licenced under a public domain dedication CC0 and stored on the Zenodo platform. The metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository which is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN (experimental programme defined for at least the next 20 years). The metadata are stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which are separate to the data itself.

For audio/video data, participants will sign a release form that provides options to have data shared within the consortium only, or open to the general public.

3.3 Making data interoperable

The [JSON Schema](#) is used as the internal representation of metadata on the Zenodo platform and export to other popular formats such as [Dublin Core](#) or [MARCXML](#) is also offered. For certain terms reference is made to open, external

vocabularies, e.g.: license ([Open Definition](#)), funders ([FundRef](#)) and grants ([OpenAIRE](#)). Each referenced external piece of metadata is qualified by a resolvable URL. In the case that uncommon or project specific ontologies / vocabularies are used/generated, mappings to more commonly used ontologies will be provided openly.

3.4 Increase data re-use

To encourage the widest possible re-use of data the metadata will be described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. Each record published in Zenodo contains a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optional, additional terms recommended by DataCite and Zenodo's own enrichments.

Analysed data generated by the CESAREF project, that has a clear scientific significance, will be validated through publication in high impact journals. The analysed data will be made public and re-usable, to permit an extensive re-use of the data, where possible. This data will be licensed with “License” being one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata, which refers to an [Open Definition](#) license. The downloaded data will be subject to the license specified in the metadata by the uploader.

The provenance of the data will be well documented, with all uploaded data and metadata being traceable to a registered Zenodo user. Furthermore, metadata can optionally describe the original authors of the published work.

All data generated during the lifetime of the project will be treated following the general process described in Figure 1 for quality assurance.

Figure 1 - Data management process for new data.

4 Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

5 Allocation of resources

The service provided by Zenodo is free of charge. The uploading of publications and data to Zenodo will be coordinated by the project manager and as such, additional costs to the project will be limited. The most notable cost associated with the output of data during the project will be related to the publication of data in high impact, open journals. These costs will be covered by the management and indirect costs budget of the local beneficiaries.

The doctoral candidates are responsible for the metadata management during the project as well as for ensuring the quality of the research results. The local beneficiaries are responsible for preservation of data produced by the doctoral candidates under their supervision. Should the preservation of all the data collected during the project not be possible, due to the quantity of data for example, the beneficiaries and the doctoral candidates will be responsible for the selection of those data to be preserved. The preserved data will be kept for as long as it is deemed useful.

The ELEANOR platform is supervised by one of the partners of the consortium. This support is free of charge for the consortium. The data is originally dedicated to the members of the consortium via a protected login. Different levels of access are available for access to a larger audience if required at a later stage of the project or after the end of the project.

6 Data security

Administrative and non-scientific data are stored on a central OneDrive file managed by the coordinator and project manager. Sensitive scientific data generated during the CESAREF project will be stored locally in our partner repositories. The security of these repositories is provided and guaranteed by the respective centres for information processing of these beneficiaries.

Access to the central OneDrive file is provided for project members and other parties upon request from a project team. This space is password protected and the security of this platform is guaranteed by OneDrive. Regular back up of all data stored on OneDrive servers is ensured. The selected data, uploaded to the dedicated OneDrive folder, will remain also available for 3 years after the end of the project.

In addition, the safety of the Zenodo repository is guaranteed according to the product description (See <https://zenodo.org/features>).

7 Ethics

According to the Annex 1 of Grant Agreement 101072625 - Part B - p. 35, the CESAREF Consortium has taken into account all requested ethics issues. For example, the most common ethical issues include:

- activities aimed at human cloning for reproductive purposes,
- activities intended to modify the genetic heritage of human beings which could make such changes heritable,
- activities intended to create human embryos solely for the purpose of research or for the purpose of stem cell procurement including by means of somatic cell nuclear transfer.

It also includes the avoidance of any breach of research integrity, which means, in particular, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct.

More precisely, all the activities carried out under the CESAREF project comply with ethical principles and relevant national, EU and international legislation, for example the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights. The tasks due to be carried out in CESAREF concern only basic research activities and will pay particular attention to:

- the principle of proportionality,
- the right to privacy,
- the right to the protection of personal data,
- the right to the physical and mental integrity of a person,
- the right to non-discrimination,
- the need to ensure protection of the environment, and,
- the need to ensure high levels of human health protection.

CESAREF will be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles. The beneficiaries commit to and ensure the respect of basic EU values (such as

respect for human dignity freedom democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights including the rights of minorities) and activities lead to the destruction of human embryos will not be carried out.

The CESAREF consortium also confirms that the activities will comply with the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity published by All European Academics and that no activities excluded from funding will be conducted. Moreover, CESAREF partners declare that the CESAREF proposal complies with:

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.
- All the data transfers will be framed by data transfer agreements between controllers. These agreements will be recorded and made available to the Commission. No personal data exports towards third countries will be performed in the project. Only import to EU countries ensuring an adequate level of personal data protection.
- Global Code of Conduct for Research in Resource poor Settings
- Standard Operating Procedures for Research Integrity
- Guidance notes on potential misuse of research results
- Guidance notes on research on refugees, asylum seekers and migrants
- Ethics and data protection
- Ethics in Social Science and Humanities
- Roles and Functions of Ethics Advisors/Ethics Advisory Boards in EC funded Projects.

All EU beneficiaries of the CESAREF project and the associated partners confirm that compliance with ethical principles and applicable international, EU and national law in the implementation of research activities not originally envisaged (or not described in detail) in the DoA will be ensured. They also confirm that any ethical concerns raised by those activities will be handled following rigorously the recommendations provided in the European Commission Ethics Self-Assessment Guidelines.